

Proceedings of the workshop

New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

In Johannesburg, 17 to 19 July 2019

University of Johannesburg, School of Tourism & Hospitality conference room

United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

UNESCO Chair
"Membrane Science applied for Environment",
University of Montpellier
(Chemistry School of Engineering)

A workshop based on a bilateral partnership between South Africa & France,
to provide a platform for various stakeholders interested in
improving the quality of water & air in South Africa

Organized with the participation & support of

Proceedings of the workshop

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New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

3-day French/South-African workshop – Johannesburg, 17-19 July 2019

• Reminder of the background & official opening

Environmental pollution is nowadays a global challenge with diverse and complicated thematic areas. It is caused by toxic chemicals emitted in the environment due to human activities (mining, agriculture, domestic waste ...) or industrial processes. This pollution affects air, water or soil, and results in the destruction of biodiversity as well as the degradation of human health. South Africa is not spared and today faces a number of specific challenges to preserve the quality of air and water. Therefore, there is a need for technology able to monitor, detects and clear all forms of pollution. This need is, even more, pressing for an emerging country like South Africa where rapid, low-cost and easy to use techniques are becoming crucial in urban, peri-urban, rural and remote areas. In this context, separation processes and membrane technologies in particular can help to solve issues through various applications.

Following the successful 2nd African Membrane Society International Congress (AMSIC) held in Johannesburg from July 29 to August 1, 2018, Abdoulaye Doucoure, president of the AMS and former student of the European Institute of Membranes (IEM) made the connection between South African researchers and French ones from Montpellier. Linkage and exchanges were facilitated thanks to Prof. Jean-Luc Pirat (ICSM – Montpellier), who already had work collaboration with the University of Johannesburg and with Prof. Xavier Yangkou Mbianda in particular.

For Many years, the European Institute of Membranes (IEM) and the UNESCO SIMEV Chair, hosted by the Chemistry School of Engineering (Montpellier, France), have organized workshops on water-related matters in developing countries, bringing solutions for sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes.

Therefore **the DST/Mintek Nanotechnology Innovation Centre, the Institute of Nanotechnology and Water – Water Node at the University of Johannesburg, and the European Institute of Membranes - UNESCO SIMEV Chair joined hands to organize the first bilateral workshop on membrane development and separation processes for water and air purification in South Africa.**

Objective: to provide a platform for various stakeholders involved in the thematic to share knowledge, network, and look at innovation opportunities in water and air treatment, thanks to

- Plenary presentations of South African challenges regarding water and air quality
- Experts sharing broad technical knowledge & real life applications of membrane based treatments
- Open discussion to foster new collaborations and help solve issues

The workshop has been co-organized by a French/South African team, coordinated by Prof. Xavier Yangkou Mbianda (Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Johannesburg) and Mathilde Boucher (UNESCO SIMEV Chair, IEM Montpellier). The event received helpful supports from UJ (DST/MINTEK, PEETS), IEM-SIMEV, the French Embassy in South Africa, NRF, ICSM, ICGM and AMS.

The workshop was open to all stakeholders interested, with free but requested online registration through the UNESCO SIMEV website (dedicated webpage). The event has been held from 17 to 19 July 2019 at the School of Tourism and Hospitality conference room, 57 Bunting Rd, Cottesloe, Johannesburg, 2092.

The official opening of the workshop has been chaired by **Prof. Debra MEYER**, Executive Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, University of Johannesburg. She introduced the event, welcoming all the speakers and participants, and gave the floor to invited representatives.

Prof. Saurabh SINHA, Deputy Vice-Chancellor: Research and Internationalization of the University of Johannesburg, built the connection between the water/air-quality “membrane” theme and the industrial revolutions. He invited us to share a reflective approach between the first and the fourth industrial revolution, the latter, through artificial intelligence, reinvigorating the next ‘water’ revolution in an era of climate change. According to him, air/water-quality assessment avenues will need a hybrid approach, for also a decentralized one. In respect of the fourth industrial revolution, the idea is to also include other technologies, for instance blockchain (water ledger), etc¹.

(Contact: dvc-r@uj.ac.za ; +27 11 559 4815 ; [link to his biography](#))

Mr Mathieu BECUE, Attaché for Innovation from the French Embassy in South Africa, then congratulated the organizers of the event for their involvement and their participation in the existing dynamics of collaboration between France and South Africa.

He insisted that the subject is extremely topical and highly sensitive in South Africa, who experienced a major crisis in the Western Cape Province last year. But it’s also critical all over the world. The recent water crisis in the Western Cape has made the need to implement more efficient and robust solutions all the more evident. Let’s also consider the case of environment contamination by acid mine drainage. South Africa is world-renowned for its mining sector, with an abundance of mineral resources, accounting for a significant proportion of global production and reserves. However, the mining sector generates high levels of exposure to environmental hazards, mainly through water and soil contamination. It is now clear that global warming, industrial activities and urban development are having a significant impact on our environment. And water is the primary medium through which the impact is being felt. To address those challenges, there is no other choice than to jointly produce innovative solutions, through combined research projects, the promotion of best practices, allowing support to adequate public policy development. In a few words, researchers, innovators, urbanists, managers, have to create technical innovations and contribute to the dialogue between science and society to tackle those major threats. The link between science and innovation through the technology transfer has to play a key role.

That why in this context, this symposium represents for him a major step in disseminating some broad technical knowledge and promoting interactive exchanges between French and South African experts focused on real life applications or practical case studies. It is also one of the evidences of the quality of the dynamics of the bilateral relationship between France and South Africa. Indeed, a dimension of growing importance of the bilateral French South African relationship is related to science, innovation and our academic relationships. The general public is not aware of the fact that France ranks 5th among the scientific partners of South Africa with more than 1000 scientific articles co-authored by researchers from both countries in 2018. The dynamism of this relationship should also be pointed out, as this number of co-authored articles has increased by an average stunning 20% per year for 5 years now. It is therefore not surprising that the bilateral agenda is rich in events related to science and technology.

This strong scientific relationship will be celebrated with the 1st French South African Science and Innovation Days, which will take the 2th and 3th of December as a side event of the [SFSA – Science Forum South Africa](#). Our scientific dialogue has attracted much attention in the political sphere. Science and technology is one of the main items discussed at the political dialogue forum which recently took place in

¹ Reference to go further: J.W. Lambrechts & S. Sinha, “Microsensing Networks for Sustainable Cities”, Smart Sensors, Measurement and Instrumentation, [Springer Nature](#), 339 pgs.

presence of our respective ministers of Foreign affairs. The French Embassy is proud to support initiatives promoting excellence in science, capacity building innovation and academic exchanges. If they can support further similar initiatives, they will do it.

Contact: mathieu.becue@diplomatie.gouv.fr

Finally, **Mr Khaya SISHUBA**, Director of the Bilateral Relations – Europe & Gulf States in the Department of Science and Technology, intervened on behalf of the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI), which shares now the same Ministry with the Department of Higher Education and Training. He highlighted how deep and broad are the SA-French science and innovation relations. The bilateral cooperation covers a wide range of activities that are mutually beneficial. The partnership covers such areas as basic research through the DST sponsored research calls, innovation partnerships, FSATI (French South African Institute of Technology) – FSAGRI, student exchanges – (i.e. HCD Nanotechnology training and exposure opportunities and added to this is the presence of French research institutions in South Africa, who supports our science partnership. In this coming December 2019, this productive and strategic partnership shall be celebrated through the [France Innovation Day](#).

He saw this workshop as one exemplar of the richness of the science relations with France. The theme talks at the very heart of the DSI policy focus on water management and its water research road map which is implemented by the Water Research Commission. Therefore, the Ministry values the strategic nature of its French relations, as it contributes to the strengthening of the national system of innovation

Science knows no borders. According to him, the success of the partnerships created must be sustainable and continue beyond the bilateral focus to an end that exploits joint research opportunities at the multilateral level, in such platforms as the EU H2020 and its future replacement and other joint research opportunities elsewhere. Equally, the partnership must also find expression in our Africa science agenda, through establishing and supporting trilateral and poly-lateral cooperations between France, South Africa and other (African) countries in our continent. Khaya Sishuba also put an emphasis to always include young people in these partnerships. The future of the science diplomacy lies in offering opportunities to them.

(Contact: khaya.sishuba@gmail.com ; +27 (0)082 944 0005; biography included in the booklet of abstracts)

• Summary & prospects

Main discussions and elements retained

Towards new collaborations & concrete projects: how to create an efficient dynamic between universities & other partners from France and South Africa?

This first bilateral workshop has completed its main objective: **to connect people**, allowing no less than 70 participants from the academic, political and industrial worlds to share their respective knowledges & expertise. It is **the first step to build new collaboration programs** and facilitate the development of adapted and sustainable technologies in line with local needs.

The research teams of the University of Johannesburg and Montpellier (IEM, ICSM, ICGM) are working on similar and complementary thematic topics, with specificities regarding local issues. Participants have made contacts and discuss the best way to start together small programs with students and SMEs. South African & French stakeholders can exchange their materials & knowledge, finding optimized solutions. Successful pilot programs could be extended in a second time.

What kind of technologies can fit to South Africa, regarding the local needs?

The idea is not to reproduce in South Africa the systems existing in France and Europe. New concepts are developed by academics here. Why not apply them in South Africa, where the needs are high? Let's take the chance to implement new systems without reproducing the mistakes which have been done in Europe (e.g. with energy and water-demanding technologies, with difficulties in treating wastewater, with costly sewage networks).

To go further and get into the details, the differences between Europe & South Africa must be specified by studying in particular the regulatory context. We are wondering about the payback of the technologies, but **the South African context & legislation also need to be detailed.**

What about municipalities? What are the issues? Are they interested? The report & conclusions of this first workshop will be shared with all the identified stakeholders and should help to enrich the dynamic: find concrete means, identify ready to be implemented technologies and go further.

How to move from the idea to the practical implementation of a technology?

Let's stop talking about implementing solutions. Researchers from UJ are building upon strong basic science. Up-scaling steps have been presented. **To take action, we need to get to the engineering of the solution.**

Unfortunately, it is noticeable that it is when the system is in crisis that other solutions are considered, such as in Cape Town with the water crisis. **The driving forces for change are closely related to (rising) costs.** What would be the cost, if we send the technology from France/ if we develop it directly from here, thanks to the transfer of technology? (Example given by Veolia, which bought containers in South Africa) It remains difficult at this stage to answer about the cost. Researchers need a specific question regarding the needs to give a precise answer.

The South African government is working on solutions, through for example the creation of the Process Energy Environment Technology Station (PEETS, presented by Dr K. Hoorzook). However, **there are still difficulties to surpass the pilot phase**. The technology transfer and innovation management has to take into account that the evolution of TRL is related to the role of the different actors. The shared finding is that **local engineers are missing to ensure the transfer of technologies**, while there is an unemployment issue for young graduated researchers. Whatever the country, *technology transfer is not easy*. How to convince investors to take up new technologies from research results? There are different models and strategies to work on, with experiences and good practices to share.

→ Creation of Start-up / Spin-off companies

Although the spin-off dynamic exists in South Africa & UJ, new companies face management difficulties after 4 or 5 years. They are often relying on a single patent, which can't be the heart of a long term company (Example of a company not existing anymore because of a bad management of IP; a resin has also been developed by NIC, which didn't reach the market for now). The same issue exists in the US and French model: *the University is really involved at the beginning to support the creation of companies. Then, after 2 or 3 years, a company should be independent with its own business model. The creation of spin-off or start-up could be a solution at the beginning. However, it often takes 3 to 5 years to implement all the innovation steps from the idea to onsite solutions.*

→ Partnership strategy with medium/large specialized companies

Another solution is to get help from existing companies, to develop a new technology with them. It will then more easily reach the market, with an exclusive or shared patent (depending on the conditions of partnership). Example of partnerships between the IEM and VEOLIA or POLYMEM: companies rely on the lab to answer their specific questions. **Facing the international competition, it is less risky and often cheaper for a company to invest in labs collaboration** rather than internalizing their R&D service. The idea is that the person who develops the technology has an opportunity to learn and test the limit of it in different contexts. It is a win/win situation.

On the model of engineering schools, the organization of student internships in industry could facilitate their integration by strengthening the link between research and industry (idea to talk with the French Embassy for funding available). Another idea would be to introduce business communication courses at the university, with the objective **to raise people awareness of existing tools and networks in the same field** (such as African Membrane Society for example).

SIMEV thematic school: share, exchange, collaborate!

In the specific and complex South African context (regarding history, geography, hydrogeology, politic, economy...), the improvement of drinking water quality and WasteWater Treatment (WWT) are addressed as health and environmental issues. Some specific local issues have been presented. A lot of people don't have access to safe drinking water (waterborn diseases) and only 11% of WW are treated (7% of WWT plants are working well). Industrial WW (mainly from mines) induces a strong pollution of surface and ground water (but who should/could pay for industrial wastewater treatment and treatment of already polluted soils and ground and surface waters?).

Water issues imply different actors - such as the government (e.g. Health, Environment, Industry, Education & Research, Agriculture, etc.), many academic and social structures (Universities, NGO, etc.), private partners - and the issues are well-known. **Decision makers are aware of problems, regulations exist. Now, solutions have to be proposed and applied**, based on capacity building, Education/training of experts and technicians (Master, Specialized school) and research programs.

- ➔ **Need of INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT of WATER : WWT and drinking water production have to be taken into account in a global vision**

- ➔ Necessity to develop simple, efficient technologies: low energy and low maintenance
 - Use of local materials (such as clays)
 - Circular economy/close the loop
 - Source separation makes the treatment more efficient
 - Train of processes adapted to specific issues (Hg, fluorides...)
 - **Sustainable energy**: energy issues in remote areas pushes us to think about solutions with less energy consumption, using renewable energy and/or recovering the energy of the process
 - **Equipment maintenance** must be integrated very early in the project, by moving towards low maintenance when designing the technology, providing technicians training locally optimizing the lifespan of the membranes (investment for a long time)

- ➔ Need to go to **advanced WWT** (μ pollutants) and **water and nutrients reuse** applications (irrigation/fert-irrigation)

- ➔ Difficulty to implement **complex technologies**: long term process (education/research + fundings). Big companies (such as Veolia) provide solutions for big cities. What about small communities? Who pays for Small companies? Small systems? Toward integrated conceptions of solutions (e.g. NIC DST MINTEK)

- ➔ Question of the public acceptance

- ➔ What about the quality assessment/control? Who is in charge? How is it organized? How can we be sure that the water is even better than the one people had before?

Perspectives and directions for concrete actions

Synergies exist! Membranes application could help to overcome some water and wastewater issues for big and small communities. South Africa offer many possibilities for drinking water and sanitation development projects. The UJ and UM common goal now, with the support of the UNESCO SIMEV Chair, is to maintain the momentum for concretizing partnerships around joint projects!

- **dissemination of this report** to the various stakeholders involved/concerned
- **Master and PhD exchanges, co-supervision for joint doctorate qualifications** between SA and France
 - contact initiated with Prof. Saurabh Sinha, Deputy Vice-Chancellor: Research and Internationalisation at UJ
 - The French Embassy already shared the opportunity to support the arrival of South African students in a French laboratory, with a few months of scholarships available this year. Waiting for feedback from colleagues to identify potential candidates.
- **Experience sharing tools**, common participation in coming thematic events
 - *Idea to create a repository to share knowledge all over Africa, relying on the network of the African Membrane Society – AMS (Ablo Doucouré)*
 - AMS 3rd International Conference, November 3-6 2020 in Dakar, Senegal
- **Seeking common funding** e.g. to thoroughly investigate the context, needs and concrete solutions available, to showcase technologies that are ready to be tested.
 - French Embassy, Campus France sponsorships
 - *Report and discussion in the frame of the [“Montpellier University of Excellence” project \(MUSE I-site\)](#) – with the 3 main pillars: Feed, protect, Care.*
 - **Horizon 2020 programs/calls** and the future edition (“FP9”): the South African Department of Science and Technology (DST) has an internal seed granting instrument for this – so this could allow for mobility of academics and for joining consortia leading application submissions (this could, for example, be in mission-oriented work around water, perhaps with artificial intelligence as supporting technology).
 - Meeting & discussion with [the Water Research Commission \(WRC\)](#) located in Pretoria
- **Signature of a broad Memorandum of Agreement (MoA) between our institutions**, as a tool to facilitate the construction of *collaborative programs*. A specific component of the MoA could be the ongoing work with the Department of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Science and under the leadership of Prof Xavier Mbianda (such an approach ensures that we’ve a broad MoA for student/staff exchange and a project annexure – allow for specific or specialist collaboration)
- **2nd workshop planned in 2021 in Montpellier**, as a good starting point for a long term agreement

List of participants

The first success of this 3-day workshop is that it allowed as many as 70 participants already concerned and involved in the thematic to make contacts towards new collaborations!

Overview of the stakeholders involved

South African academic participants **46**

UJ - University of Johannesburg	31
WITS - University of the Witwatersrand	1
UNISA - University of South Africa	4
TUT - Tshwane University of Technology	3
UNIVEN - University of Venda	2
University of Limpopo	1
Medical Research Council	1
MINTEK	3

French academic participants **9**

IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes / UNESCO SIMEV	7
ICSM - Institut de chimie Séparative de Marcoule	1
ICGM - Institut Charles Gerhardt Montpellier	1

Government officials / policy makers **5**

WRC - Water Research Commission	1
Department of Science & Technology - SA Government	2
French Embassy	2

Industrial representatives **6**

VEOLIA	2
Sibanye Stillwater Gold Mining South Africa	1
Eskom	1
Hollingsworth & Vose / African Membrane Society	1
FGWRS/FIRMS France	1

Other representatives of civil society **4**

Eco International	1
SABC Digital News in Auckland Park	1
Others	2

Detailed list of the 70 participants

Full Name	Institution	Country	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
			62	52	51
ADENIYI Amos	Tshwane University of Technology	South Africa	1	1	
AYINDE Wasiu Babatunde	University of Venda	South Africa	1	1	1
BECUE Mathieu	French Embassy	South Africa	1		
BHEMBE Yoliswa	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1		
BOPAPE Mokgadi	Tshwane University of Technology	South Africa	1		
BOUCHER Mathilde	UNESCO SIMEV	France	1	1	1
CHABALALA	University of South Africa - UNISA	South Africa	1	1	1
CHAUKE N.M.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
CHUKWUATI Christopher	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
DARAMOLA Michael	University of the Witwatersrand	South Africa	1	1	1
DERATANI André	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	
DOUCOURE Abdoulaye	African Membrane Society / Hollingsworth & Vose	USA	1	1	1
E VAN DER MERWE Roelof	Eco International	South Africa	1	1	1
GAXELA Nelisa	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
GOVENDER Vashlin	VEOLIA	South Africa	1		
GUES Marion	French Embassy	South Africa	1		
GUMBI Nozipho	University of South Africa - UNISA	South Africa	1	1	1
HERAN Marc	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	1
HOORZOOK Kousar	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
LANGERMAN Kristy	University of Johannesburg	South Africa			1
LESAGE Geoffroy	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	1
LEUDJO Taka	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
LURULI Ndivhuwo	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1		1
MAGNES Pierre	FGWRS/FIRMS France	Monaco	1	1	1
MAHLAHLA Sesona	SABC Digital News in Auckland Park	South Africa	1		
MAHLANGU Sydney	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MAKHETHA Andretta	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MALEFO Lebethé	University of Johannesburg	South Africa		1	1
MALINGA Soraya	University of Johannesburg	South Africa			1
MAMBA Nosisa	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MASEBINU Samson	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MASIBI E.G.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MATEBESE F.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MBULI B.S	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MEYER Debra	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1		
MIELE Philippe	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	1
MLASI Bongani	MINTEK	South Africa	1		
MOFOKENG Mookgo	University of South Africa - UNISA	South Africa	1	1	1
MOGOLODI Dimpe	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MOLELEKWA Fred	Tshwane University of Technology	South Africa		1	
MOUTLOALI Richard	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
MPFUNZENI Raphulu	CID	South Africa	1	1	1
MUDZIELWANA Rabelani	University of Venda	South Africa	1	1	1

Full Name	Institution	Country	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
MUJUNRU Munyaradzi	University of Limpopo	South Africa	1	1	1
NCUBE Somandla	University of South Africa - UNISA	South Africa	1	1	1
NDEKETEYA Annah	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1		1
NEL Bultie		South Africa	1	1	
NKWE Sylvester	Sibanye Stillwater Gold Mining South Africa	South Africa	1	1	1
NOMADODZI Lufono	MINTEK	South Africa	1		
NOMFUNDO Masilela	University of Johannesburg	South Africa		1	1
NOMNGONGO Philiswa	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
NQOMBOLO A.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
PELLET-ROSTAING Stephane	ICSM - Institut de chimie Séparative de Marcoule	France	1	1	1
PIRAT Jean-Luc	ICGM - Institut Charles Gerhardt Montpellier	France	1	1	1
POCHAT Céline	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	1
RAMONTJA James	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
SAURABH Sinha	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1		
SIKHONZILE Sikhosana	Department of Science & Technology - SA Government	South Africa	1	1	1
SIKHWIVHILU Keneiloe	MINTEK	South Africa		1	
SIKOSANA Mmontshi	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
SISHUBA Khaya	Department of Science & Technology - SA Government	South Africa	1		
SISILANA S.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
SUNDARARAJAN Parani	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
TSEKA Tebogo	Eskom	South Africa	1	1	1
WERNECKE Bianca	Medical Research Council	South Africa			1
XABELA S.	University of Johannesburg	South Africa	1	1	1
XU Leon	VEOLIA	South Africa	1		
ZAVISKA François	IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes	France	1	1	1
ZVINOWANDA Caliphs	University of Johannesburg	South Africa		1	
ZWIMBA John	Water Research Commission	South Africa	1		

- **Review of the detailed program: photos, presentations & abstracts**

The booklet of abstracts has been sent to all the participants just before the workshop and is now available on SIMEV's website (<http://www.unesco-simev.org/en/>) and online repository (https://zenodo.org/communities/unesco_simev/). It gathers the contacts of all the speakers, with their short biography and abstracts.

The detailed program reported here below highlights the presentations for which you can reach the full content (links included when available).

New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

Wednesday, July 17

8:00 to 8:55 *Welcoming and installation of the delegates*

Words of Welcome

by University of Johannesburg Officials / French High commission representatives/ DST Representatives

Chair: Prof Debra MEYER (Executive Dean Faculty of Sciences - University of Johannesburg)

9:10 to 9:20 **Professor Saurabh SINHA** - Deputy vice Chancellor Research of the University of Johannesburg

9:20 to 9:30 **Mr Mathieu BECUE** - Attaché for Innovation - French Embassy in South Africa

9:30 to 9:40 **Mr Khaya SISHUBA** - Director: Bilateral Relations - Europe & Gulf States, Department of Science and Technology

Official opening chaired by Prof. Debra MEYER, with Prof. Saurabh SINHA, Mr Mathieu BECUE and Mr Khaya SISHUBA (respectively).

9:40 to 10:00 **[Steps to advance membrane & filtration sciences in Africa: Perspectives from the African Membrane Society.](#)** *Invited speaker: Dr Abdoulaye DOUCOURE, AMSIC*

10:00 to 10:45 *Group picture & coffee break*

Wednesday, July 17

Global environmental protection - Water quality in urban areas

Presentation of SA challenges – focus on large-scale issues

Chair/Moderators: A.Prof. R. MOUTLOALI & Prof MIELE

Time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation
10:50 to 11:10	<u>Non-occupational environmental risk assessment from exposure to mercury in the gold mining environment of Witwatersrand basin, South Africa.</u> <i>Invited speaker: Sylvester NKWE</i>	NGO
11:10 to 11:30	<u>Treatment of Brine for the Recovery of Drinking Water, Calcium Carbonate and Sodium Sulphate.</u> <i>Invited speaker: Dr Munyaradzi MUJURU</i>	University of Limpopo
11:30 to 11:50	<u>Circular Economy Model For Water And Wastewater Management</u> <i>Invited speaker: Dr John Ngoni ZVIMBA</i>	Water research Commission
11:50 to 12:10	<u>Water Treatment Technologies Research and Development at the DST/Mintek Nanotechnology Innovation Centre.</u> <i>Invited speaker : Dr Keneiloe SIKHWIVHILU</i>	NIC DST/MINTEK
12:15 to 13:30	Lunch break	

Global environmental protection - Water quality in urban areas

Expertise and potential solutions

Chair/Moderators: A.Prof C. POCHAT & Prof NOMNGONGO

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation
13:30 to 13:50	<u>Introduction to Process Energy Environment Technology Station (PEETS) and an overview of Effective Microorganisms in the treatment of Fresh water system.</u> <i>Invited Speaker : Dr Kousar Banu HOORZOOK</i>	PEETS, UJ
13:50 to 14:10	<u>A solution to save our drinking water resources: grey water recycling</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Pierre MAGNES</i>	Firmus France
14:10 to 14:30	<u>Urbanization & Decentralised Treatment of water: challenges to take up in order to enhance reuse & valorisation.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. Marc HERAN</i>	IEM
14:30 to 14:50	<u>Water Reuse Opportunities for Municipal and Industrial Players</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Leon XU</i>	VEOLIA
14:50 to 15:10	Alternative Methods for Metals Recovery - Chemical Complexation and Extraction Technologies. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Stephane PELLET-ROSTAING</i>	ICSM
15:10 to 15:40	coffee break	
15:40 to 16:00	Organophosphorus compounds: synthesis, complexing abilities & applications. <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. Jean-Luc PIRAT</i>	ICGM
16:00 to 17:00	Discussions around points raised during the day – conducted by Marc HERAN & colleagues	

Thursday, July 18 - SIMEV thematic school (1)

Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes - Energy supply

Presentation of challenges – focus on small-scale issues

Chair/Moderator: Prof RAMONTJA + P. MAGNES

9:00 to 9:10	<u>Introduction & Presentation of the UNESCO SIMEV Chair</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Mathilde BOUCHER</i>	SIMEV
9:10 to 9:40	<u>Introduction to IEM - Expertise, know-how and facilities</u> <u>With a focus on nanostructured interfaces for membrane applications</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Prof Philippe MIELE</i>	IEM
9:40 to 10:00	<u>Water treatment issues in South African rural areas: overview of the context.</u> <i>Invited speaker: Dr Somandla NCUBE</i>	UNISA
10:00 to 10:30	coffee break	

Thursday, July 18 - SIMEV thematic school (2)

Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes - Energy supply

Expertise and potential solutions: part I

Chair/Moderator: Prof. PIRAT

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation
10:30 to 10:50	<u>Use of Local Clays for the Remediation of Ground Water in Rural Areas</u> <i>Invited speaker: Dr Rabelani MUDZIELWANA</i>	University of Venda
10:50 to 11:20	<u>Membrane technologies & Their Applications to the Mining Industry</u> <i>Invited Speaker: A.Prof Céline POCHAT</i>	IEM
11:20 to 11:40	<u>Polymer Nanocomposite Membranes and Resins Research for wastewater remediation.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: A.Prof Richard MOUTLOALI</i>	University of Johannesburg
11:40 to 12:00	Innovative membrane processes coupling to face new water challenges. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr François. ZAVISKA</i>	IEM
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch break	

Expertise and potential solutions: part II

Chair/Moderator: A.Prof R.MOUTLOALI + Dr F. ZAVISKA

13:30 to 13:50	<u>Treatment of wastewater and effluent re-use in small communities</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Caliphs ZVINOWANDA</i>	University of Johannesburg
13:50 to 14:10	<u>Membrane bioreactor for urinary nitrogen stabilization: microbial acclimation and system performance.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Geoffroy LESAGE</i>	IEM
14:10 – 14:30	<u>Strong Institutional Arrangement for Sustainable Membrane Filtration Water Supply in Rural Communities: a case of Tshaanda, Limpopo, South Africa.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Fred MOLELEKWA</i>	TUT
14:30 to 14:50	<u>Solar powered desalination units for small communities and remote locations: case study of plants located in Africa using the Osmosun® technology.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr André DERATANI</i>	IEM/Mascara
14:50 – 15:20	coffee break	
15:20 -15: 40	Treatment of Water effluents and Water re-use Hair Saloon and personal care products. <i>Invited Speaker: Giovanna BENNETT (TBC)</i>	L'Oreal South Africa
15:40 – 16:40	Discussions around points raised during the day conducted by Geoffroy Lesage & colleagues	
16:40 - 17:30	Poster Session	

Sustainable clean water in small communities through membranes processes

18th STM Thematic School - Johannesburg, 18 July 2019

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNESCO Chair "Membrane Science applied for Environment", University of Montpellier (Chemistry School of Engineering)

Posters presented by South African PhD students on Thursday afternoon.

Friday, July 19

Moderators: Dr MALINGA + S. PELLET-ROSTAING

Global environmental protection: Air quality

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation
9: 00 - 9:20	<u>Air pollution and human health - a South African perspective</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Bianca WERNECKE</i>	South African Medical Research Council
9:20 – 9:40	<u>Performance Assessment of Metrobus Diesel Dual Fuel Buses towards a Soot Free Transport.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Samson MASEBINU</i>	PEETS, UJ
9:40 – 10: 00	<u>Addressing air pollution in dense low-income settlements through air quality offsets.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Kristy LANGERMAN</i>	Department of Geography, UJ
10:00- 10:20	Molecular Filtration Media for Improved Air Quality. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Abdoulaye DOUCOURE (TBC)</i>	Hollingsworth & Vose (HV) - USA
10:20 to 10:50	coffee break	

Potential collaborative projects & Conclusion

10:50 to 11:10	<u>International training & cooperation tools available in Montpellier.</u> <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. P. MIELE</i>	Montpellier University
11:10 to 11:30	Research support and international collaboration opportunities available at the University of Johannesburg. <i>Invited speaker: Dr Ndivhuwo LURULI & Lebetho MALEFO</i>	University of Johannesburg
11:30 to 11:50	Summary and conclusion: Future collaborative projects and overall perspectives. <i>Chair LOC (Prof. XY MBIANDA)/ Chair Mont. (Prof. P. MIELE)</i>	UJ / UM
Lunch break		

Visit of UJ laboratories – Friday, July 19

visit of the UJ laboratories for members of the French delegation (*Philippe MIELE, Stephane PELLET-ROSTAIN, Geoffroy LESAGE, Celine POCHAT, Jean-Luc PIRAT, Mathilde BOUCHER, Pierre MAGNES*) guided by UJ colleagues (*Xavier MBIANDA, Richard MOUTLOALI, Caliphs ZVINOWANDA*) and students.

Opposite : Philippe MIELE (IEM-ENSCM), Xavier MBIANDA (UJ) & Jean-Luc PIRAT (ICGM -ENSCM).

